

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF "ALPOMISH" AND "BARCHINOY" SPECIAL TESTS IN IMPROVING THE HEALTH LEVEL OF THE POPULATION, INVOLVING POPULAR SPORTS AND PROMOTING A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE

Dusyarov Salimjon Khudaimuratovich

Teacher of Termiz State University

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ABSTRACT

One of the important tasks is to improve and increase the level of health of the population, to educate young people to be physically healthy, strong, mentally and spiritually mature, to develop and strengthen their physical qualities. Special tests "Alpomish" and "Barchinoy" that determine the level of physical fitness and health of the population serve as an important tool in the implementation of these goals and tasks.

To date, attention to physical education and sports in our country is implemented at the level of state policy. To improve and strengthen the level of health of the population, to systematically promote a healthy lifestyle among the population, to further strengthen the principles of a healthy lifestyle in society, to protect the growing young generation from harmful habits and every a neighborhood, educational institutions, in order to form a system of effective organization of physical education and sports activities in work teams and others, on January 29, 2019, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Widely promoting a healthy lifestyle in Uzbekistan and involving the population in physical education and public sports to "About" decision No. 65 was adopted.

Based on this decision, the organization of the "Alpomish" and "Barchinoy" tests, which include the sports norms that determine the general physical fitness of the population, depending on the age, in the form of a competition between the broad segments of the population, and the winners and prize-winners Regulation on the procedure for accepting and conducting competitions of "Alpomish" and "Barchinoy" special tests, which determine the level of physical fitness and health of the population, promotion with III, II, and I level badges, "Alpomish" and the regulation on "Barchinoy" badges, description of "Alpomish" and "Barchinoy" badges and certificates, on the development of national sports and folk games in order to further increase the popularity of sports in Uzbekistan the program of measures, the program of measures for the development of sports games was approved.

Also, to the relevant and responsible ministries, agencies, organizations, to accept the "Alpomish" and "Barchinoy" special tests, which determine the level of general physical fitness and health of the population, in the form of a competition, to prepare badges and

certificates, to reward the winners and prize-winners, 2019 Starting from February 10, 3-5 minutes mass physical education videos will be aired three times a day (morning, afternoon and evening) on all TV channels, regularly comprehensive coverage of the goals and tasks of this decision among the population, working hours recommendations and tasks such as organization of industrial gymnastics, quarterly summarization of information about the work being carried out are set.

Chapter 5, Clause 33, Chapter 1 of the Regulation on the procedure for accepting and conducting competitions of "Alpomish" and "Barchinoy" special tests, which determine the level of physical fitness and health of the population. General rules (items 1-8), chapter 2. Purpose and tasks of special tests (items 9-10), Chapter 3. The system of special tests (items 11-29), (§ 1. Organization of competitions on special tests, § 2. Conducting the competition), Chapter 4. Procedure for awarding winners and prize-winners (items 30-32) and Chapter 5. Consists of final provisions (items 33).

The purpose of special tests is to develop physical education and sports among all strata of the population to develop them physically and intellectually, to improve their physical ability and movement activity, to achieve physical and mental maturity, to increase their ability to work, to prevent harmful habits and various diseases, and to be healthy. from the formation of healthy lifestyle skills, the strengthening of qualities such as will, confidence in one's own strength and capabilities in young people through sports competitions, the development of courage, patriotism and loyalty to the Motherland, and the organization of systematic work on the selection of talented athletes from among young people consists of.

The tasks of special tests are as follows:

- a) expanding the ranks of citizens engaged in physical education and sports;
- b) increase the level of physical capabilities of the population;
- c) achieving physical strength, fitness and health of the population, training them in sports, incorporating physical education and sports into their daily lifestyle;
- g) to improve the knowledge and skills of the population on special physical education and sports;
- d) further development of sanitation works in rural areas and villages of our country;
- e) to contribute to the physical fitness, fitness and health of young students, especially girls, to their training with sports, to incorporate physical education and sports into their daily lifestyle;
- j) is to encourage the growing young generation to follow a healthy lifestyle, to achieve spiritual and physical perfection, and to increase their enthusiasm for physical education and sports.

Special tests are divided into the following 12 age groups:

- Group 1 — 6-8 years old;
- Group 2 — 9-10 years old;
- Group 3 — 11-12-year-olds;
- Group 4 — 13-15-year-olds;
- Group 5 — 16-17-year-olds;
- Group 6 — 18-25-year-olds;
- Group 7 — 26-33-year-olds;

- Group 8 — 34-41 years old;
- Group 9 — 42-49 years old;
- Group 10 — 50-59 years old;
- Group 11 — 60-69 years old;
- Group 12 — 70 years and older.

Assessment of the level of physical fitness of the population is carried out on the basis of performance specified in special tests. Such tests demonstrate the quality of basic physical development, movement knowledge and skills of a person in relation to his gender and age.

The types of tests are divided into two, they consist of mandatory tests and optional tests.

- Compulsory tests to develop the following physical qualities based on the specified level and level of complexity:

- a) level of development of endurance capabilities;
- b) level of development of power capabilities;
- c) focused on the level of development of flexibility capabilities.

- Voluntary tests to develop the following physical qualities based on the specified level and level of complexity:

- a) the level of development of speed and voltage capabilities;
- b) the level of development of the ability to coordinate actions;
- c) is aimed at the level of development of acquired practical skills.

Competitions held on the basis of special tests are held at the level of institutions, organizations, neighborhoods, inter-neighborhoods and districts (city), regions and the Republic on the basis of the established plan and approved regulations agreed with the relevant ministries, authorities, local departments and departments.

It is recommended to hold the "Alpomish" and "Barchinoy" competitions in three stages based on the following age categories:

- 1st stage — from 6 to 17 years old;
- 2nd stage — from 18 to 33 years old;
- Stage 3 is for those aged 34 and over.

The report on the winners of the competition will be drawn up, the winners and prize-winners will be awarded "Alpomish" and "Barchinoy" badges (with a certificate) according to the established order, and may be awarded with souvenirs from organizations, as well as special records are determined in the process of taking tests.

Organized and held tests and competitions, depending on the age, gender and health level of the population and participants, shuttle running, jumping rope (1 minute) or multiple jumps (on one leg), hitting a tennis ball from 6 meters to a 1x1m target, Gymnastics climbing the wall, pulling up on the horizontal bar, writing with bent arms resting on the floor or sitting with arms stretched forward, kicking a soccer ball from 3 meters into a 1.5x1.5 m goal, from a gymnastic seat bending forward without bending the knees (calculated from the bottom of the foot), raising the legs together in a row to 900 while lying on a shovel, raising the body while lying on the back, legs in a low bar, stretching forward and pulling up in a position touching the ground, Tennis ball throwing, Darts (hitting a target from 2 m.), knocking a 45 kg dummy by the waist (to the right and left sides), holding a 45 kg doll by the arm and waist (to the right

and left), lifting a 10-16 kg sports equipment (gyra) pull up, throw a basketball into the basket from 3 m, hit a 20x20 cm target 5 m away with a tennis ball, run 60, 100, 1000, 2000, 3000 m, get up and run long jump, throw of 150-300-500-700 gr, free swimming 25-50-100 m, walking 5 km, hiking on the slopes of the mountains 5 km, Scandinavian walking 1-3 km, lifting and lowering a sports equipment (3 kg dumbbell) with one hand, pulling up on a low bar, rolling a basketball and knocking down kegels 2 m away, holding a gymnastic ladder and sitting down are used. When taking into account the results of the participants in the organized tests and competitions, and awarding badges and ranks, the age and gender of the participants are differentiated and determined.

In conclusion, it can be said that the special tests "Alpomish" and "Barchinoy" help the population, especially young people, to grow up healthy and well-rounded, to mature physically and intellectually, to improve their physical abilities and movement activity, and to achieve physical and mental maturity, in the increase of work capacity, in the prevention of harmful habits and various diseases and in the formation of healthy lifestyle skills, in the strengthening of qualities such as will, confidence in one's own strength and capabilities in young people through sports competitions, in them courage, patriotism and loyalty to the Motherland it serves as an important tool in character development, selection and selection of talented athletes among young people.

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